

THE DEGREE OF ARAB SCHOOL PRINCIPALS' COMMITMENT WITHIN THE GREEN LINE TO THE CODE OF ETHICAL CONDUCT AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO SCHOOL PERFORMANCE FROM THE TEACHERS' POINT OF VIEW

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Abstract

The study was aimed at identifying the degree of commitment of Arab school principals within the Green Line to the Code of Ethical Conduct, as well as its relationship to school performance as viewed by teachers. The descriptive, correlational survey method was adopted, with the questionnaire serving as a data collection tool. It was applied to a sample of (401) male and female teachers selected at random. The findings revealed that Arab school principals within the Green Line had a high degree of commitment to the Code of Ethical Conduct from the perspective of teachers, that Arab schools within the Green Line had a high degree of school performance, and that there was a statistically significant correlation between the degree of commitment of Arab school principals within the Green Line to the Code of Conduct. Morale and academic performance.

Keywords: Degree of Commitment, The Code of Ethical Conduct, School Performance, The Green Line.

INTRODUCTION

One of the important aspects that education seeks to form is the moral aspect, and what has increased interest in the subject of morals is the moral preparation of employees, which, if applied effectively, provides a conscious and committed administrative and leadership elite that can extend its direct influence on the commitment and discipline of others who work under its authority, and this leads to... As a result, the entire administrative apparatus follows the system and moral ideals. Following ethics is something that everyone must be mindful of, and management should not rely on employees' personal convictions to assess the amount of their commitment to the ethics of their job. It is necessary to define what is ethical and what is unethical according to the institution's custom so that everyone adheres to it, and it is necessary to deal firmly in the event of a violation of these ethics, as it cannot be accepted that there is an overlap between the interests of individuals and the interests of the institution. Ensuring professional ethics is a professional and administrative matter, and professional ethics is a fundamental component of development that must be prioritised among employees and administrators (Brooks & Dunn, 2020).

To achieve its goals in the field of moral education, especially as a refinery for education and education, every human element in it, from the teacher to the school staff and all the way up to the director, must have an appropriate level of competence and be able to bear the consequences of his duties to the fullest extent (Nasser, 2006). The leader in his school is expected to exhibit high levels of commendable moral behaviour that is consistent with the teaching profession's code of ethical conduct, in order to win over the employees, start with them where they are, and raise them to where they should be, achieving the best possible positive and good results. Work progress and adherence to the code of ethical conduct are critical, as they strengthen commitment to the principles of correct and honest work, prevent the educational institution from viewing its interests through a narrow lens that only accommodates specific standards, and provide benefits in the short and long term (Arar & Saiti, 2022).

The dedication of school principals to the code of ethical conduct in the educational process is seen as the foundation for constructing the school community with all of its components and activities (Al-Bashiriya, 2015). In the absence of this Code and adherence to it, corruption spreads in its many forms, as does the spread of manifestations of lack of trust and empowerment, the lack of activation of participatory management, and the exaggerated use of bureaucracy, which was reflected in educational institutions in features of authoritarianism, lack of delegation, and reduction of power. For more details, see Yahya (2010).

The ethical constitution of any profession is considered binding on its members, and is closely linked to human behaviour, according to the Code of Ethical Conduct for the Profession of the School Principal, issued by the Ministry of Education through the Education Profession Development Authority in the year (2017). The school principle is held accountable for guiding all efforts and forces that he encounters within the scope of his work and directing them to accomplish the desired results. He is accountable for the school's work in terms of its efficacy and progress, as well as for providing and arranging the required facilities for the educational process. The school principal will not be able to do all of his tasks successfully unless he is proficient in a variety of talents and has a strong work ethic. According to Abu Hamdi (2018), the code of ethical conduct in the educational institution serves as the foundation for the balanced conduct and management of the educational process. To achieve the educational philosophy that aims for interaction and engagement, aside from the administrative routine that educational environments suffer from, to supplement it with the right alternative, resulting in a qualitative shift in educational institutional performance. School performance as a whole comprises school administration performance, which symbolises the coordinated efforts made by all school employees, including administrators and technicians, to achieve school goals. It also incorporates teachers' and students' efforts (Shatnanawy, 2015).

According to Williams (2003), the process of increasing institutional performance is built on four pillars: internal processes, organisational structures, human resources, and technology. These topics have quickly gained popularity and spread, becoming among the top priorities and primary concerns of institutions trying to achieve greatness. The first decade of the twentieth century was known as the "Performance Measurement Era." According to Al-Sharman and Al-Omari (2022), the administrative leadership's commitment to ethical practises

based on the Code of Ethical Conduct increases feelings of belonging and loyalty among employees towards the educational institution, prompting them to exert their best efforts at work, makes them feel job satisfaction, stability, and security, and contributes to raising the rate of achievement at work. If the administrative leadership did the reverse and biased people over others, and discriminated against people over others, this damages their emotions of belonging and loyalty, reduces their enjoyment of work, and instills hatred for others and hatred of officials in them. The circumstance may have resulted in internal turmoil and the dissemination of slander and suspicions about this administrative leadership.

The successful leader is the one who applies the functional code of conduct to the educational process in such a way that it corresponds to the nature of the administrative work he performs, which consists of making choices and taking on duties.

As a result, administrative leadership's failure to enforce the code of professional conduct reduces administrative work efficiency. As a result, educators are concerned with evaluating the performance of school principals in order to develop these competencies, as the evaluation process in any system constitutes an important field in determining the needs of those special systems. It identifies the abilities and competences that require remedial development through training and development. It is also utilised as a source of feedback for system personnel to understand the system's perspective on their performance (Al-Khabaz, 2016).

For several years, the Green Line's Department of Education has worked to improve institutional performance of employees in all areas of the educational process, raise student achievement levels, improve the system in place, in order to develop performance, and work to build programmes that meet the needs and goals of the school. It has provided several Initiatives, including the Discipline and Respect Initiative, the Computerised Interactive Education Initiative, the Standardised Examinations Initiative, the Computerised Teachers' Performance Evaluation Initiative, and the School Principals' Performance Evaluation Initiative (Ministry of Education and Higher Education, 2018).

The Code of ethical conduct:

The Green Line's code of ethics imposes numerous obligations and standards on teachers, both male and female, at schools. The Code is a document that explains the principles, abilities, commitments, and behaviours that distinguish male and female teachers as certified professionals. The goal of the Code of Ethics for Education and Faculty is to establish teachers' right to define their professional status and make independent decisions about the content of their work.

Education and teaching personnel are aware of the scope of their responsibilities to their profession and the ramifications for their students, students' parents, the community, The co-workers in the profession, and educational authorities. As a result, a code of professional ethics for teaching and learning personnel that establishes a permanent framework for reference, deliberation, evaluation, and conduct is critical.

The site emphasises many topics about the profession, others on students, a third about The co-workers, and a fourth about parents. The following are the most notable of these points (Ministry of Education, 2023):

1. The professional mission of education workers and teachers is to impart knowledge, develop learning abilities, and develop students' multifaceted personalities, with the goal of achieving their best: as individuals who realise their latent potential, as citizens who participate and contribute to society, and as human beings who expand and shape their personalities from convergence to the achievements of world culture, to the origins of Jewish culture in all its degrees.
2. To achieve these goals, educators and teachers will work to foster an educational climate and educational encounters based on mutual trust and respect, the development of quality in thought and action, social care, the development of the joy of learning and mutual enrichment, and the nurturing of a perpetual learner - curious, educated, rational. His knowledge is the "tree of life" for himself and society, being critical, sensitive, gregarious, and creative. Basic obligations
3. Do everything in their power to promote their students' healthy development and well-being, to prevent harm to and abuse of their bodies and minds, and to provide appropriate development conditions for each of them, while taking into account and accepting the following: difference, and concern for the progress of struggling students.
4. Work to promote and strengthen fundamental human and democratic ideals, as well as the legacy of heritage. Education refinement, quest of truth, openness and thinking, freedom, responsibility, equality, justice, respect for man and the way of the country, peace - tolerance and solidarity, as represented in national laws and the United Nations Charter on "Human Rights" and "Children's Rights."
5. Carry out their professional responsibilities in an acceptable manner, prevent any act or omission that may jeopardise the profession's honour, and serve as a personal example of the traits that the educational endeavour strives to create.
6. They are continuously striving to improve their professional and pedagogical talents, and in the process, they establish and initiate activities and programmes in their areas of competence, as well as in the educational activities of the institution where they work.
7. Apply contemporary scientific information, educational principles, and teaching methods while maintaining intellectual honesty, justice, and an open environment.
8. Emphasize constant inspection of the educational institution's work qualities, ongoing efforts to develop them, and delivering responsible and reliable reports to the relevant public about their work in those areas within the framework of their professional obligation.
9. Avoid withholding or misleading information about their professional experience and abilities

10. Preventing persons who are recognized to be unsuited to teach due to a lack of skills or training from entering the profession.
11. Refrain from abusing their position of authority and influence in order to further their personal agendas, advance their political and ideological viewpoints, or advance activities and duties that fall outside the purview of their roles as educators and teachers.
12. Be obedient to the educational "I Believe" and pedagogical concerns of the organisation where they are employed, as well as to the pertinent governmental authorities.
13. A strong work ethic, as well as a willingness to take initiative and accept accountability for one's actions within the educational setting.
14. Instill in pupils intelligence, critical thinking, morality, and life skills. Do everything within your power to help them reach their greatest potential while taking a considerate and compassionate approach to their individual requirements. -entity.
15. Offering pupils a range of viewpoints and stances in a democratic, pluralistic manner while fostering in them the capacity to analyse and evaluate differing viewpoints on their own and make the best decision possible.
16. Providing equal treatment to all of their students, abstaining from discrimination on the basis of nationality, race, gender, origin, political viewpoint, socioeconomic standing, or any other basis, and honouring the demands of their bodies. Their worldview and their belongings.
17. To be vigilant and perceptive to the student's reported concern and endeavour to alleviate it, in collaboration with parents and/or professional entities within the school and community.
18. Relying on their best professional judgement and pedagogical conscience, as well as a fair approach and harmony with the pedagogical values and foundations that underlie pedagogical practise, base their evaluations on students' accomplishments.
19. Handle disciplinary issues in line with the principles of the Code of Ethics, the rules of the Ministry of Education, the institution's charter, or other regulations in order to collaborate with students to create a set of rules that must be followed for proper conduct. among the campus community.
20. Honour each student's right to accurate information about their academic and social circumstances, whether from their parents or guardians, and utilise that knowledge to better their circumstances and social and academic accomplishments.
21. Make sure that all information about the student, his parents, or his family is kept private and secret. Unless the student gives permission, do not share any material that has come to your attention as a result of your work as an educator. For the student and their parents, unless specifically mandated by state law or strictly professional grounds (and even then, only for authorized officials). Don't talk about kids' personal or family issues unless it's really necessary for their education.

22. Make every effort and show compassion to guarantee the students under their care are safe and secure both physically and mentally.
23. Only allow their students to participate in research or experiments with written consent from the appropriate authorities.
24. Promoting parental involvement and collaboration in the academic and educational progress of their children in the educational institution, as well as striving to establish dialogic relationships and uphold mutual trust and respect, based on the understanding of the professional authority of educators and teaching staff and their accountability for the work done and knowledge acquired there, on the one hand, and parents' primary duty and obligation to their children, on the other.
25. Treat every parent of a student with dignity and equality; refrain from treating them unfairly on the basis of their socioeconomic standing, level of education, nationality, race, gender, religion, place of origin, political beliefs, or any other factor.
26. Giving parents an accurate and current report on their children's social and academic standing, as well as information about the policies and processes in place at the school.
27. Take care to uphold the strict confidentiality of any personal information about the student's family or parents, unless it is necessary for their academic work and is provided with the parents' consent. Information will only be provided without parental consent if it is necessary due to state laws or strictly professional considerations, and even then, only to authorised officials.
28. To treat their coworkers with dignity and refrain from doing harm to others in their name or honour, whether verbally or in writing.
29. Strive to create an environment at work where collaboration, helpful criticism, support, and cross-pollination are valued. To support coworkers in their work, share professional experiences and expertise with them, collaborate to accomplish the goals set forth for them in terms of education, and help with the assimilation and integration of new teachers and education professionals into the educational establishment.
30. Unless it's necessary for strictly professional reasons or state laws, and even then, only for authorised officials, refrain from bringing personal details about a colleague in the profession that have been brought to their attention from internal or external sources.
31. Cooperate with other members of their profession's team to stop any harm from being done to anyone's body, dignity, or educational standing, as well as to parents, teachers, students, and other members of the public and government institutions.
32. The educator should make every effort to avoid disparaging, verbally or in writing, the reputation or name of a colleague, whether they work for the same organisation or not.
33. The educator should make every effort not to damage the reputation of the organisation where he works or the education system overall, as their reputation is his shame and their reputation is his honour.

34. The teacher will prioritise working collaboratively with his peers for the benefit of the profession at the professional educational level. He will offer them—or the organisation where he works—his guidance and experience, as well as any reference materials, literary sources, and research findings that come to his attention and that, in some way, could improve the institution's educational efforts.
35. When a teacher learns intimate personal information about a colleague professor from sources both inside and outside the institution, he is not allowed to disclose it to the public.
36. When making judgements about professional education, teachers should try to avoid using their position within the system to unfairly influence their The co-workers.
37. The educator stays away from unjust professional rivalry with his peers and makes an effort to direct his justifiable goals and desires into the most constructive and innovative avenues.

Adherence to ethical rules of behaviour and the teaching profession's ethics have been the subject of numerous studies. Abu Hamdi's study (2020) used the descriptive survey method and a questionnaire as a tool for data collection and analysis in order to uncover teachers' adherence to the Code of Professional Conduct's ethics from the perspective of Aqaba Governorate school principals. It was applied to a sample of fifty-six male and female principals, and the findings demonstrated that, from the perspective of the school principals in the Aqaba Governorate, teachers' adherence to the principles of the Code of Professional Conduct was, for the most part, substantial. Furthermore, the results demonstrated that there were no statistically significant differences resulting from the two academic qualification variables, and that there were statistically significant differences pertaining to the gender variable in favour of females in the degree of teachers' commitment to the ethics of the Code of Professional Conduct. also expertise.

In order to determine the institutional performance and how it related to the managerial abilities of middle school principals in the Baghdad Education Directorate, Azab (2020) carried out a study. He collected data using the questionnaire and the descriptive approach. A sample of sixty male and female principals were subjected to it. The findings demonstrated that the principals' institutional performance Middle schools embraced the idea of institutional performance with all of its components, and school principals scored highly; nevertheless, middle school principals have superior administrative skills and institutional performance.

In 2020, Kasa et al. carried out a study in the Pendang region of North Peninsular Malaysia to investigate the association between the ethical perspective of the school principal and the level of dedication exhibited by national secondary school teachers. A descriptive survey method was employed, with a questionnaire serving as a tool for data collection and analysis. The sample comprised 254 male and female teachers. The findings demonstrated that teacher dedication is significantly impacted by the ethical field. These types of leaders need to blend their values and actions with internal moral standards. There are no appreciable differences, and this strategy needs to alter the atmosphere and affect the attitudes of the teachers. Statistics pertaining to the gender and teaching experience characteristics.

The Al-Amrat study (2020) used a descriptive correlational approach, a questionnaire was used to collect data, and the study sample consisted of 250 randomly selected male and female teachers. The study's goal was to identify the professional practises of school principals and their relationship to promoting school excellence in the Petra Education Directorate from the perspective of teachers. The study's findings demonstrated how well qualified school principals were in their field. The outcomes also demonstrated the high calibre of academic achievement in the institution. The findings showed that professional practises had a statistically significant positive link with improving school excellence as well as a statistically significant effect on promoting school excellence.

Al-Mutairi (2021) also carried out a study that sought to clarify the challenges faced by the division members and determine the efficacy of the divisions' efforts to raise academic performance in middle schools in the State of Kuwait. Utilising the descriptive survey approach, the questionnaire served as a tool for data collection and analysis. The study sample consisted of 120 members from the school performance improvement divisions of government middle schools in Jahra, Farwaniya, and the capital. The findings demonstrated that, in accordance with the questionnaire's objectives, the sample members' assessments of the efficacy of the work done by the school performance enhancement divisions were moderate.

The goal of Musa's study from 2021 was to determine how committed public school administrators in the city of Nablus actually are to professional ethics and codes of conduct, as well as how best to advance them from their perspective. He employed a qualitative methodology based on interviews, and the study population was the 87 principals of public schools in the city of Nablus. Six managers were specifically chosen to have their data collected from. The findings demonstrated that the managers had a high level of commitment to both the code of conduct and professional ethics, that the code does not directly evaluate the managers, and that indirect methods are used to assess and gauge the managers' level of commitment to the code. It is subjective and contains a number of elements that should be removed, the most notable of which are those that deal with the tension between the principal's authority and the rules and laws enforced by the Ministry of Education.

In their study, Odigwe and Owan (Odigwe & Owan, 2022) looked at how secondary school principals in the Nigerian Calabar Metropolis manage both financial and non-financial resources to meet institutional objectives. The questionnaire served as a tool for data collection while the quantitative method was applied. The outcomes demonstrated that it was applied to a sample of sixty-nine principals and assistants. The accomplishment of institutional objectives is closely related to how school administrators handle their financial resources. The accomplishment of institutional goals in secondary schools has also been found to be significantly correlated with the way in which school principals handle non-financial resources, such as school libraries, records, and human resources. The management of financial and non-financial resources in public secondary schools is essential to achieving educational goals.

To the best of the researchers' knowledge, no prior studies have addressed the relationship between school performance and the code of ethics, and those that have varied in terms of the study population. Therefore, the current study stands out from earlier research on the topic of

Arab school principals' commitment to the code of ethics and how it affects school performance. as well as the application's location and sample.

Based on the aforementioned, it is evident from the researchers' observations that principals' adherence to the Code of Conduct varies, and this disparity poses a significant barrier to the advancement of education. As a result, in order to improve their performance, school principals need to be prepared with extra care and attention. This may be done by hosting training sessions on the ethical behaviour system and strengthening their dedication to it. Professionally, and to enhance their capacity to carry out their duties and cultivate their cognitive and performance competencies, which align with the evolving roles they are expected to play within the context of their administrative and leadership responsibilities in a long-term, all-encompassing, integrated manner; and to ameliorate the standard of living in their schools in order to raise the quantity and quality of school performance in their educational establishment. As a result, this study was able to ascertain the level of dedication that Green Line school principals had to the code of ethics and how it connected to teachers' perceptions of student achievement.

The Study Problem:

The study's challenge is defined by attempting to uncover the relationship between Arab school principals' commitment to the Code of Ethical Conduct within the Green Line and its relevance to school performance from the perspective of teachers. This is accomplished by responding to the following questions:

- 1- How committed are Arab school principals within the Green Line to the Code of Ethical Conduct from the perspective of teachers?
- 2- From the perspective of instructors, what is the level of school performance in Arab schools within the Green Line?
- 3- Is there a statistically significant link at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the level of school performance and the degree of commitment of Arab school principals within Al-Akhdar to the code of ethical conduct?

Objectives of the study

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- 1- Identify the degree of commitment of Arab school principals within the Green Line to the Code of Ethical Conduct from the point of view of teachers, in order to shed light on it to strengthen it and improve the degree of commitment to it.
- 2- Identify the level of school performance of Arab schools within the Green Line from the point of view of teachers, with the aim of improving and enhancing it.
- 3- Explaining the extent to which there is a correlation between the degree of commitment of Arab school principals within Al-Akhdar to the code of ethical conduct and the level of school performance, in order to evaluate each of them if such a correlation exists.

Significance of the Study

Its theoretical significance is proved by studies on the code of ethical conduct for school principals and the level of school performance and the relationship between them, as well as the scientific addition it may provide to the Arab library. It may pique the curiosity of academics who explore the subject in different ways, and its recommendations may serve as a springboard for future research.

Its practical significance is proven by providing feedback to those responsible for teaching in schools along the Green Line on how well school administrators adhere to the code of ethical behavior. Because of its significant impact on achieving educational process goals, the findings of this study may benefit those responsible for selecting school principals in terms of the importance of adhering to them in administrative work, as well as teachers in Green Line schools. This is through their understanding of their principals' commitment to the code of ethical conduct, and its role in maintaining the educational process's progress in accordance with the set goals, and it can open new horizons for researchers to conduct more of these studies in various aspects related to the study.

Definition of Terms:

❖ The study includes the following terms:

- **The School Principal's Code of Ethical Conduct:** "A self-reference for the principal to guide him in administrative work, as well as an internal monitor through which he carries out his professional practises, determines his relationships with others, and adjusts his behaviour in accordance with its provisions." It also assists him in performing his duties and fulfilling his rights, as well as emphasising his role in serving society." "Treat him well, and grant him legal benefits that preserve his dignity and respect, which reflects positively on his psychological stability and degree of commitment" (Ministry of Education, 2017, 5). Procedurally, it is known as: a code issued by the Ministry of Education in 2017 that specifies the standards that school principals must follow within the educational process with teachers, students, parents, and members of the local community, and the degree of adherence to it was measured through the response of the study sample members to the tool developed for this purpose.

-**The term "performance of schools"** refers to "A management philosophy and a comprehensive administrative approach based on the principle of good and superior investment of school resources and their efficiency and investing them optimally to achieve the goals of the educational process" (Shawqi, 2012, pp. 12-13). In this study, it is referred to as the overall score obtained by respondents on the study tool designed to assess school performance.

Limitations of the Study:

The results of the study are determined in the light of the following limits:

❖ Limitation in terms of the objective: This study limited to identifying the degree of Arab school principals' commitment within the green line to the code of ethical conduct and its relationship to school performance from the teachers' point of view

- ❖ The constraints imposed by humanity: This study was limited to a sample of teachers in Arab schools within the Green Line.
- ❖ Spatial limitation: limited to Arab schools within the Green Line.
- ❖ Time limitation: The study was implemented in the second semester of the 2022/2023 academic year.

Study Determinants: Study limitations: The generalizability of the results of the current study is determined by the tools used to collect data and the extent to which they have acceptable psychometric properties (validity and reliability), and the extent, objectivity, and honesty of the respondents.

METHOD AND PROCEDURES

- ❖ **Study methodology:** The descriptive, correlational survey method was adopted for its suitability for the purposes of the study.
- ❖ **Study population:** The study population consisted of all male and female teachers in Arab schools within the Green Line, numbering (7569) male and female teachers, according to statistics from the Ministry of Education for the academic year (2022 AD).

The Study Sample

A random sample was selected from the study population, which consisted of (401) male and female teachers.

Instrument of the Study

A questionnaire was constructed to collect the data necessary to achieve the objectives of the study. It consisted of two parts: First, it included personal data. Second, it consists of two axes: First, to measure school principals' commitment to the code of ethical conduct. Second, to measure the level of performance. For the purpose of formulating the paragraphs of the first axis, we referred to theoretical literature and previous studies related to the topic, such as the study of Abu Hamdi (2020); Musa (2021). (33) paragraphs were drafted in their initial form, distributed into four areas. To formulate the paragraphs of the second axis, reference was made to the study of: Azab (2020); Al-Amrat (2020), where (35) paragraphs were drafted in their initial form, distributed into four areas.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

Content validity of the instrument:

The Instrument was presented in its initial form to a group of experts and specialists in the fields of: educational administration and pedagogy, higher education administration, curricula and teaching methods, and measurement and evaluation, in a number of universities, numbering (10) arbitrators, with the aim of expressing their opinions on its paragraphs in terms of belonging and clarity of wording, language, and any modifications they deem appropriate. Based on the arbitrators' comments and opinions, the proposed amendments were made, which

consisted of amending the wording of paragraphs (2, 11, 19, 24, 26, 30), and deleting paragraphs (6, 8, 15). As for the second axis (school performance); The wording of paragraphs (36, 39, 48, 55, 56) was modified, paragraphs (38, 41) were deleted, and paragraph (50) was separated to become two paragraphs, so that the number of paragraphs in the first axis became (30), and their number in the second axis (33). Paragraph, with (63) paragraphs in the tool with its two axes.

Construct validity of the instrument: The Instrument was applied to an exploratory sample of (30) male and female teachers, from outside the target study population, to calculate the values of Pearson correlation coefficients for the relationship of the paragraphs to the axis and to the fields that belong to it, and Table (1) shows this.

Table (1): Pearson correlation coefficients for the Fields items with the field to which they belong, and with the axis as a whole (n=30)

The first Field, which is the Code of ethical conduct												
Item link to		Item No	Domain	Item link to		Item No	Domain	Item link to		Item No	Domain	
Field	Domain			Field	Domain			Field	Domain			
0.80**	0.78**	21	local community	0.78**	0.84**	11	The co-workers	0.69**	0.80**	1	The Profession	
0.59**	0.60**	22		0.83**	0.81**	12		0.86**	0.89**	2		
0.83**	0.79**	23		0.84**	0.89**	13		0.70**	0.85**	3		
0.53**	0.58**	24		0.77**	0.87**	14		0.77**	0.82**	4		
0.83**	0.91**	25		0.84**	0.82**	15		0.81**	0.87**	5		
0.86**	0.92**	26		0.76**	0.83**	16	0.79**	0.83**	6			
0.79**	0.87**	27		0.68**	0.81**	17	0.65**	0.70**	7			
0.72**	0.83**	28		0.82**	0.85**	18	0.87**	0.89**	8			
0.77**	0.85**	29		0.82**	0.91**	19	0.86**	0.90**	9			
0.82**	0.85**	30		0.83**	0.85**	20	0.82**	0.90**	10			
The second field : the level of school performance												
Item link to		Item No	Domain	Item link to		Item No	Domain	Item link to		Item No	Domain	
Field	Domain			Field	Domain			Field	Domain			
0.73**	0.73**	53	Social relations	0.73**	0.78**	42	Scholl	0.57**	0.76**	13	Administrative performance	
0.77**	0.73**	54		0.75**	0.85**	43		0.53**	0.67**	32		
0.68**	0.67**	55		0.75**	0.83**	44		0.79**	0.88**	33		
0.68**	0.68**	56		0.74**	0.80**	45		0.82**	0.79**	34		
0.72**	0.79**	57		0.87**	0.85**	46		0.67**	0.79**	35		
0.62**	0.77**	58		0.67**	0.78**	47	0.56**	0.72**	36			
0.77**	0.82**	59		0.77**	0.77**	48	0.55**	0.67**	37			
0.61**	0.73**	60		0.76**	0.80**	49	0.66**	0.72**	38			
0.76**	0.82**	61		0.86**	0.90**	50	0.77**	0.78**	39			
0.73**	0.81**	62		0.73**	0.81**	51	0.77**	0.74**	40			
0.76**	0.84**	63		0.57**	0.68**	52	0.72**	0.73**	41			
the environment												

It is noted from Table (1) that all correlation coefficients were of acceptable and statistically significant degrees, and therefore none of these items were deleted.

Reliability of the Instrument

For the goal of examining the instrument's internal consistency; The instrument 's internal consistency and reliability coefficients are displayed in Table (2). The instrument was reapplied

to the exploratory sample with a two-week interval between applications, using Cronbach's α equation based on the data from the first application of the exploratory sample and for the purpose of verifying the stability of the instrument, its two axes, and their fields.

Table (2): Cronbach alpha coefficients and reliability of the Instrument, its two fields and their domains

The first field: Code of ethical conduct			
Item No	R	Cronbach Alpha	Domain
7	0.96**	0.92	The Profession
8	0.98**	0.95	The co-workers
7	0.98**	0.90	Students
8	0.95**	0.93	local community
30	0.99**	-	Ethical behavior
The second field : the level of school performance			
Item No	R	Cronbach Alpha	Domain
8	0.94**	0.88	Administrative performance
7	0.89**	0.89	school environment
8	0.92**	0.90	Learning and teaching
10	0.97**	0.92	Social relations
33	0.97**	-	School performance

It is noted from Table (2) that the values of the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficients for the domains of the (Code of Ethical Conduct) axis ranged between (0.90-0.95), while the reliability values for the domains of the same axis ranged between (0.95-0.98), and the value of the repetition reliability coefficient as a whole was (0.99), and it is also noted that the values of the Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients for the areas of the axis (level of school performance) ranged between (0.88-0.92), while the values of the reliability of repetition for the areas of the same axis ranged between (0.89-0.97), and the reliability coefficient of repetition was on the axis of the level of school performance. As a whole (0.97).

Standard correction of the study instrument

The statistical model with proportional grading was adopted; With the aim of making judgments about the arithmetic means of the study tool, the fields that belong to it, and the paragraphs that belong to the fields, this is done by dividing the range of numbers (1-5) into five categories to obtain the range of each level, ($5-1/5 = 0.80$). Accordingly, the levels will be as follows:

Class of arithmetic media

Mean	Performance level	Degree of practice
5.00-4.20	Very High	Very High
-3.40 less than 4.20	High	High
-2.6 less than 3.40	Moderate	Moderate
-1.80 less than 2.6	Low	Low
-1 less than 1.8	Very Low	Very Low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Firstly. Results of the first question, which stated: “What is the degree of commitment of Arab school principals within the Green Line to the Code of Ethical Conduct from the point of view of teachers?”

To answer this question; Arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the degree of school principals’ commitment to the code of ethical conduct, and Table (3) shows this.

Table (3): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the degree of school principals’ commitment to the code of ethical conduct on the domains in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Field & Domain	Domain Number	Rank
High	0.50	4.07	The Profession	1	1
High	0.54	4.01	Students	3	2
High	0.55	3.98	Local Community	4	3
High	0.57	3.87	The Co-Workers	2	4
High	0.49	3.98	Total		

The findings presented in Table (3) indicate that the school principals' arithmetic means for the various areas of their commitment to the Code of Ethical Conduct ranged from 3.87 to 4.07. Based on their arithmetic means, all of them were categorized as having a high degree of commitment, and they were ranked in the following order: the profession came in first, followed by the fields of students, the local community, and coworkers.

As the principle is regarded as the perfect example for all facets of the educational and pedagogical process, whether within or outside the school, this may be because of his intense desire to possess moral values as an incentive for all those working with him to possess these qualities. Maybe it's because the principal of the school values and honors his job, works honestly, keeps appointments and times punctual, and sets a good example for others by being trustworthy, exercising self-control, and not abusing his position for personal gain. He also takes criticism in a productive way without getting attached or zealous.

His coworkers hold him in high regard and expect him to uphold these values, particularly given his sensitive role as an educational leader who is ultimately responsible for upholding the highest standards of professionalism and ethics. The current study's findings concurred with those of Abu Hamdi's (2020) study, which demonstrated instructors' strong adherence to the code of professional conduct's ethical standards.

It also supported the findings of the study conducted by Kasa et al. (Kasa et al, 2020), which demonstrated that teacher dedication was significantly impacted by the ethical field. It also concurred with the findings of Musa's study from 2021, which demonstrated managers' strong adherence to the ethics and code of conduct of their profession.

We also computed the arithmetic means and standard deviations for each field's elements, yielding the following results:

A: Field of profession: The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the items in the field of profession, and the results were as in Table (4)

Table (4): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for items in the field (profession) arranged in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Items	Item No	Ranking
High	0.75	4.16	He adheres to the laws and instructions issued by the Ministry of Education	7	1
High	0.74	4.15	He is keen to adhere to school hours	6	2
High	0.75	4.09	The manager's behavior reflects his commitment to religious values towards his profession	1	3
High	0.70	4.06	He is characterized by honesty and carrying out his responsibilities well	2	4
High	0.76	4.04	Adheres to the ethics of the teaching profession	3	5
High	0.76	4.00	Commitment to scientific integrity in all cases and circumstances	5	6
High	0.81	3.96	He works to constantly update his knowledge of his specialty	4	7
High	0.50	4.07	Total		

The results in Table (4) make it evident that the profession field items have an arithmetic mean of 4.07 and a standard deviation of 0.50. The Ministry of Education's statute, which mandates that school principals keep regular hours, be devoted to their work, follow laws and regulations, and not injure the profession, may be the cause of this. Anyone who tries to break these rules and directives faces consequences. Principals can also attend workshops and training sessions offered by the Ministry of Education. Since school principals are the highest ranking members of the educational hierarchy and are tasked with enforcing rules and regulations without showing partiality or discrimination, they are eager to uphold the code of professional conduct for the teaching profession, which should be made clear to schools, particularly the newly established ones. With a mean of (4.16) and a standard deviation of (0.75), paragraph (7)—which declares that the author "adheres to the laws and instructions issued by the Ministry of Education"—received the highest grade, indicating a high level of devotion. Maybe this is because principals of schools They understand how crucial it is that they follow the rules and guidelines that the Ministry wants the principals to follow. In order to support the educational process, the Ministry of Education also regularly collaborates with school principals to develop laws and guidelines. Principals understand the significance of following these directives, which enables them to make informed decisions about their administrative responsibilities. The statement in paragraph (4), "He works to constantly update his knowledge of his specialty," was the least committed, with a mean score of 3.96 and a standard deviation of 0.81. Maybe because the individuals in the study sample believe they are living as the leaders of the educational pyramid in their institutions, school principals must adapt their administrative

skills to keep up with the rapid advancements in science and technology in a society where these fields are rapidly changing. Principals have also lately attended workshops on self-development offered by the Ministry of Education. To understand their responsibilities in light of this evolution and assist them in resolving the issues they encounter.

B. The field of co-workers: The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the items in the field of co-workers, and the results were as in Table (5)

Table (5): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for items in the field (coworkers) arranged in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Items	Item No	Ranking
High	0.77	3.94	He takes mutual respect as a basis for building his relationships with his colleagues	10	1
High	0.85	3.92	He avoids mentioning his colleagues' shortcomings in front of others, if any	8	2
High	0.78	3.90	He is humble in his dealings with his colleagues	11	3
High	0.82	3.90	He keeps his colleagues' secrets.	13	3
High	0.79	3.89	He is quick to provide assistance to his colleagues when they need it	14	5
High	0.82	3.84	He accepts constructive criticism from his co-workers.	9	6
High	0.87	3.84	He performs his work fairly among his colleagues	15	6
High	0.93	3.69	He suppresses his anger at the harassment of his colleagues	12	8
High	0.57	3.87	Total		

The results in Table (5) show that the arithmetic mean for the items in the field of coworkers is (3.87), with a standard deviation of (0.57), indicating a high level of commitment. Perhaps this is due to school principals' knowledge of the importance of human interactions at work, their emphasis on the social component, and their interest in their teachers and assisting them in their professional development. Members of the survey sample also believe that their principals tolerate criticism, can engage in constructive discourse, and strive to provide everything necessary. Teachers attain greatness and success in the educational process for a variety of reasons, one of which is that the Ministry of Education inside the Green Line consistently attempts, through its official books, to urge principals to pay attention to teachers and provide incentives to the distinguished. The highest ranking for paragraph (7), which states, "He takes mutual respect as a basis for building relationships with his colleagues," came in first place, with an arithmetic mean (3.94), a standard deviation (0.77), and a high level of commitment. Perhaps this is due to the school principals' awareness. Because of the importance of the teacher, as he is considered the focal point of the educational process and change in any society, school principals have begun to involve teachers in all school decisions, through committees, so the teacher has become a partner even in administrative decisions, so Principals build respectful relationships with their fellow teachers. While paragraph (12), which declares, "He suppresses his anger at the harassment of his colleagues," finished last with a mean (3.69), standard deviation (0.93), and a high level of commitment. Perhaps this is because the study

sample members believed that school principals needed to have excellent morals, which is one of the components of good leadership. Their repression of anger has a good impact on the behaviors of those who work with them, as well as the impact of training programmes and courses offered for them in this regard.

C. Student domain: The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the students' domain items, and the results were as in Table (6)

Table (6): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for items in the field (Students) arranged in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Items	Item No	Ranking
High	0.66	4.12	He looks at the students with compassion and fatherhood.	16	1
High	0.71	4.08	He works to be a good role model for students.	17	2
High	0.82	4.01	It accepts students of all social backgrounds.	22	3
High	0.75	4.00	He thinks well of his request	18	4
High	0.74	3.97	He makes every effort to develop all aspects of student development	19	5
High	0.78	3.96	Students are granted their rights in accordance with regulations and laws	20	6
High	0.82	3.92	He respects the opinions of his students and accepts them with open arms	21	7
High	0.54	4.01	Total		

The results in Table (6) show that the students' domain items have an arithmetic mean of (4.01) and a standard deviation of (0.54), indicating a high level of commitment. Perhaps this is due to their idea that their principals' relationships with their students must be positive, as seen by their academic achievement and enthusiasm for school. Furthermore, the function of school principals extends beyond routinely overseeing the work of teachers to accepting students, assisting them in resolving problems, and involving them. This is what the Ministry of Education does in its choices by directing principals to pay attention to students by involving them in school committees and activities. Paragraph (16) received the highest grade, which stated: "Students are viewed with compassion and fatherhood." First and foremost, with an arithmetic mean of (4.12), a standard deviation of (0.66), and a high level of dedication. This could be because school principals are essentially parents before they enter the teaching profession, so they want to treat their children well, be kind to them, and strive for excellence. To achieve excellence in their schools, all employees and students must have humane and good relations, and our religion teaches us to treat children well by being kind to them and encouraging them to excel and succeed in their academic careers. While paragraph (21), which declares, "He respects his students' opinions and accepts them with open arms," came in last place with a mean of (3.92), a standard deviation of (0.82), and a high level of commitment. Perhaps this is related to the teachers' belief that effective management is the outcome of It encompasses all pillars of the educational process, and their principals are continually looking for ways to implement counsel with students by allowing them to choose the activities that suit

them. Most school principals hold special sessions with students to listen to their comments and take what is appropriate for the learning process, demonstrating the principals' respect for their students' viewpoints.

D. The local community domain: The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the items in the local community domain, and the results were as in Table (7)

Table (7): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for items in the field (local community) arranged in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Items	Item No	Ranking
High	0.71	4.10	Parents are provided with accurate information about their children	23	1
High	0.70	4.05	Answers parents' inquiries about their children	24	2
High	0.75	4.00	Adheres to public morals and social customs.	27	3
High	0.74	3.98	Adheres to public morals and social customs.	25	4
High	0.81	3.96	Be a good role model for the people of his community in his words and actions	29	5
High	0.79	3.94	Strengthens the relationship between the school and the local community	30	6
High	0.84	3.93	He calls on the people of his community to reject fanaticism and racism through his meetings with them	28	7
High	0.85	3.85	He adheres to the principles of integrity and transparency in his work	26	8
High	0.55	3.98	Total		

The results in Table (7) show that the arithmetic mean of the items in the local community field (3.98), with a standard deviation (0.55), indicates a high level of commitment. This could be because its management are convinced of the community's dominant beliefs, customs, and traditions, which favorably affect the process. Administrative and educational, because members of the local community are educational partners who provide ongoing assistance to schools. Perhaps this is because the Ministry of Education has recently emphasized the value of community engagement with parents and the local community, as represented by its institutions, and has begun to stress principals by incorporating them in school committees as representative members. For the benefit of the local community. Aside from the research sample members' understanding that the school is an educational institution that cannot be separated from the surrounding community, as it both influences and is affected by it. The most points were awarded to paragraph (23), which states: "Parents shall be provided with accurate information about their children." First and foremost, with a mean (4.10), standard deviation (0.71), and a high level of dedication. This could be because the study sample members believe that parents are true partners of the school, and that they must know their children's levels and collaborate with the school to solve their children's difficulties. This is accomplished through parent council meetings held by the school, as mandated by the Ministry of Education. While paragraph (26), which states: "He adheres to the principles of integrity and transparency in his

dealings with parents," came in last with a mean (3.85), standard deviation (0.85), and a high level of commitment. Perhaps this is due to the fact that school principals do The administrator must strive for honesty and integrity in his work by documenting their work in particular records, just as kids are a mirror of what happens at school and convey all that happens to their homes.

Second: The results of the second question, which stated: “What is the level of school performance of Arab schools within the Green Line from the point of view of teachers?”

To answer this question; The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the axis of school performance level and its domains, taking into account the order of the domains in descending order according to their arithmetic means, and Table (8) shows this.

Table (8): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the level of school performance on the domains, arranged in

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Field & Domain	Domain number	rank
High	0.51	4.01	Administrative performance	1	1
High	0.53	3.98	school environment	2	2
High	0.52	3.95	Learning and teaching	3	3
High	0.56	3.88	Social relations	4	4
High	0.48	3.95	Total		

It is noted from the results in Table (8) that the arithmetic means for the areas of school performance level for Arab schools within the Green Line ranged between (3.88-4.01), and the performance level was high. The reason for this is attributed to the tireless efforts made by the Ministry of Education within the Green Line to raise the level of performance of school principals, as the Ministry of Education provided many training programs and workshops for principals on excellence in administrative work, which reflected positively on raising the level of school performance. The reason is also that school principals within the Green Line carry out their work and tasks in accordance with drawn up plans, use performance measurement indicators to clarify the level of progress achieved, and deal seriously with the suggestions submitted by parents and the local council to improve school performance. As for the areas of the tool: All of them achieved a high level of performance, as the field of (administrative performance) came in first place, with an arithmetic mean (4.01) and a standard deviation (0.51). The reason may be attributed to the teachers’ view of the school principal as someone who follows up the progress of the educational process in the field, activates school activities, supervises the effectiveness of the use of school facilities, plans in a realistic manner, and distributes tasks and work to school employees in accordance with educational regulations and instructions. This result may indicate The school principal is keen to transfer ideas, expertise, experiments and educational innovations to his employees by involving them in training programs and workshops, and working to translate them into procedural plans within their schools. It was followed in second place by the field (school environment), with a mean (3.98) and standard deviation (0.53). The reason for this high level may be attributed to teachers’ conviction and satisfaction with the role of school administration, which strives to create a safe and stimulating educational environment for creativity and excellence, especially since there is

a growing interest on the part of educators and those in charge of education in schools within the Green Line to improve school environments and use pedagogical methods. Modern and follow up on it. Finally, there was the field of (social relations), with a mean (3.88) and standard deviation (0.56).

The reason for this may be attributed to the personal traits that distinguish school principals within the Green Line from his experience in administrative work, such as: humility, respect for others, cooperation, teamwork, and motivation. These qualities helped strengthen his communication with everyone around him, including colleagues. The results of the current study agreed with the results of Azab's (2020) study, which showed that the institutional performance of male and female school principals was high. It also agreed with the results of the Al-Amrat study (2020), which showed that the level of school excellence was high. While it differed with the results of Al-Mutairi's study (2021), the effectiveness of the work of the divisions to improve school performance in middle school schools was moderate. Arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the items in each field separately, and the results were as follows:

A. The field of administrative performance: The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the items in the field of administrative performance, and the results were as in Table (9)

Table (9): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for items in the field (administrative performance) arranged in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Items	Item No	Ranking
High	0.66	4.19	Develop a strategic plan for the school	31	1
High	0.69	4.08	Develop an annual operational plan	32	2
High	0.72	4.02	Follow up on the progress of the educational process	37	3
High	0.75	3.99	Carrying out its work and tasks according to pre-prepared plans	33	4
High	0.81	3.98	Coordination between teachers to achieve school goals	38	5
High	0.75	3.96	Completing its administrative transactions within the specified time	34	5
High	0.77	3.94	Determine the training needs of teachers	35	7
High	0.75	3.94	Determine priorities aimed at improving students' performance	36	8
High	0.51	4.01	Total		

The results in Table (9) show that the arithmetic mean for the administrative performance items is (4.01), and the standard deviation is (0.51). With a mean of (4.19), a standard deviation of (0.66), and a high level of performance, paragraph (31), which states "developing a strategic plan for the school," came in top position. This is due to the fact that school principals work within purposeful steps based on planning, coordination, and organization, which is a result of the strategic plans that school leaders prepare in collaboration with their teachers at the start of the school year. The strategic plan also outlines the concepts of school work and the activities

that will take place during the school year. This eliminates unpredictability from schoolwork and brings it into order, increasing performance. With a mean of (3.94), a standard deviation of (0.75), and a high level of performance, paragraph (36) finished in last place, stating, "Setting priorities that aim to improve students' performance." The explanation for this could be that school principals are concerned about the quality of educational outcomes and direct teachers to serve kids to the best of their abilities. Furthermore, the school management is eager to give all educational supplies within schools in a method that improves students' grades and advances their intellectual and practical levels.

B. School environment domain: The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the items in the school environment domain, and the results were as in Table (10)

Table (10): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for items in the field (school environment) arranged in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Items	Item No	Ranking
High	0.65	4.13	Security and safety procedures are implemented within the school	39	1
High	0.71	4.04	Classrooms have adequate ventilation and lighting	40	2
High	0.74	4.03	The school has adequate water and electricity	41	3
High	0.85	3.94	Sanitary conditions are available in the school environment	45	4
High	0.80	3.94	The school environment is clean and beautiful	44	5
High	0.79	3.92	The school has learning resource rooms	43	6
High	0.83	3.89	Teachers and students have an educational environment that encourages creativity	42	6
High	0.53	3.98	Total		

The arithmetic mean for the items in the school environment field is (3.98), and the standard deviation is (0.53), as shown in Table (10). With a mean (4.13), standard deviation (0.65), and a high level of performance, paragraph (39) came in top position, stating: "Security and safety procedures are implemented within the school." The explanation for this could be that school principals provide all safety needs in their schools in accordance with Ministry of Education legislation and policies. To provide a risk-free educational environment in order to protect the health and safety of students, staff, and visitors to the school. The school administration also contributes to the provision of technology and equipment to assist in detecting risk areas and properly preparing to address them, as outlined in the school's strategic plan. While paragraph (42), which claims, "Teachers and students have an educational environment that encourages creativity," came in last place with a mean of (3.89), a standard deviation of (0.83), and a high degree of performance. The reason for this could be attributed to the fact that the school administration contributes to refining and developing students' creativity by providing school playgrounds, computer laboratories, the Internet, and theaters, as well as school gardens in which students practice their interests in a way that suits their inclinations, abilities, and skills, and invests in their talents and directs them on sound paths and destinations that benefit them

and others. The society. The school administration also satisfies the needs of instructors by providing them with new technologies, instructional aids, laboratories, and other resources that allow them to deliver the educational process to pupils in an entertaining and appealing manner.

C. Field of learning and teaching: Means and standard deviations were calculated for the items in the field of profession, and the results were as in Table (11)

Table (11): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for items in the field (Learning and Teaching), arranged in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Items	Item No	Ranking
High	0.67	4.11	The plans prepared by the teacher are comprehensive in terms of general and specific goals	46	1
High	0.71	3.96	The teacher uses communication skills in the classroom	47	2
High	0.78	3.95	The school provides the laboratories needed by the educational process	52	3
High	0.74	3.94	The teacher takes into account individual differences among students during teaching	49	4
High	0.76	3.93	The teacher uses all types of assessment to evaluate students' performance	48	4
High	0.77	3.92	Teachers diversify their use of modern teaching strategies	51	4
High	0.77	3.90	The teacher employs modern information technology in teaching	50	7
High	0.86	3.87	The school provides adequate Internet access.	53	8
High	0.52	3.95	Total		

Table (11) shows that the arithmetic mean of the level of school performance for the learning domain items is (3.95), with a standard deviation of (0.52). With a mean of (4.11), a standard deviation of (0.67), and a high level of performance, paragraph (46), which states, "The plans prepared by the teacher are characterized by comprehensiveness in terms of general and specific goals," took first place. The explanation for this could be that the school administration arranges regular meetings for teachers to learn about the realities of the educational process and to direct them to implement all general and specialized curricular goals. Furthermore, school principals are kept up to date on teachers' preparation and attend class sessions to observe how successfully instructors are implementing general and specific goals and provide criticism.

While paragraph (53), which declares, "The school provides the Internet appropriately," finished last with a mean of (3.87), a standard deviation of (0.86), and a high degree of performance. This could be related to the school administration's confidence in the Internet's relevance in advancing the educational process. It assists teachers in displaying instructional scenes and photos linked to the subject of the lesson, inspires teachers to submit tasks for students to do at home, and assists teachers in expanding their knowledge by investing their leisure time in a beneficial way. In addition, they must participate in electronic training courses. The Internet assists the teacher in completing all of the work and duties assigned to him within

the school by raising students' grades on electronic platforms, responding to inquiries from students and their parents, and others.

D. The field of social relations: The arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the items in the field of social relations, and the results were as in Table (12)

Table (12): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for items in the field (Social Relations) arranged in descending order

Degree	Standard Deviation	Mean	Items	Item No	Ranking
High	0.71	4.05	The school creates a positive atmosphere that makes teachers feel optimistic	54	1
High	0.76	3.94	Teachers react positively to the problems they face within the school	55	2
High	0.77	3.93	Students practice group work with their classmates in the classroom	58	3
High	0.74	3.92	Teachers within the school work collaboratively	56	4
High	0.79	3.87	Local community participation has a positive impact on improving school performance	60	5
High	0.75	3.86	The school offers various activities that serve the local community	61	6
High	0.76	3.85	The relationship between the students themselves is characterized by respect and cooperation	59	7
High	0.79	3.85	The school provides volunteer work that serves the local community	62	8
High	0.90	3.78	The school involves the local community in its decision-making	63	9
High	0.92	3.77	The local community participates in solving students' problems within the school	57	10
High	0.56	3.88	Total		

Table (12) shows that the arithmetic mean of the level of school performance for the items in the subject of social connections is (3.88), with a standard deviation of (0.56). With a mean of (4.05), a standard deviation of (0.71), and a high level of performance, paragraph (54), which declares, "The school creates a positive atmosphere that makes teachers feel optimistic," took first place. The explanation for this could be because school principals make teachers feel important and play an important role in the educational process by bringing them close to them, identifying their difficulties at school and outside of school, and providing them with the necessary support. All of this contributes to a creative instructional atmosphere for teachers. In addition, the school administration strives to spread love and tolerance among all instructors, as well as to eliminate any hostility amongst them, allowing teachers to feel the warmth of the educational environment. While with a mean of (3.77), a standard deviation of (0.92), and a high level of performance, paragraph (57), which declares, "The local community participates in solving students' problems within the school," placed in last place. This can be attributed to the fact that the school administration activates the partnership with the local community and

invites them to the programs and activities held within the school, which has contributed to the development of good relations between the school and the local community. The school administration also draws on the knowledge of the local community to run awareness workshops for kids in order to keep them safe in the event of a catastrophe.

Third: The results of the third question, which stated: “Is there a statistically significant correlation at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the degree of Arab school principals within Al-Akhdar’s commitment to the code of ethical conduct and the level of school performance?” To answer this question; Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between the Code of Ethical Conduct axis and its domains and the Performance Level axis and its domains, and Table (13) shows this.

Table (13): Values of the correlation coefficients of the axis of the degree of school principals’ commitment to the code of ethical conduct and its areas and the axis of the level of school performance and its areas

Total for the second Filed	Social relations	Learning and teaching	school environment	Administrative performance	Statistician	Impact
0.73**	0.57**	0.66**	0.67**	0.74**	Correlation coefficient	The Profession
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Statistical significance	
0.79**	0.73**	0.69**	0.67**	0.72**	Correlation coefficient	The co-workers
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Statistical significance	
0.78**	0.63**	0.68**	0.72**	0.78**	Correlation coefficient	Students
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Statistical significance	
0.83**	0.71**	0.73**	0.72**	0.82**	Correlation coefficient	local community
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Statistical significance	
0.86**	0.73**	0.76**	0.77**	0.85**	Correlation coefficient	Total for the first Filed
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Statistical significance	

The results in Table (13) show that there is a statistically significant positive connection at the significance level ($= 0.05$) between the level of school performance and the degree of commitment of Arab school principals within Al-Akhdar to the Code of Ethical Conduct. This suggests that the more the dedication of Arab school principals in Al-Akhdar to the Code of Moral Behavior, the higher the level of school performance. As a result, school principals must maintain this commitment, and any lapse will reflect badly on the level of school performance. Because principals would then have abandoned their commitment to the code of ethical conduct in the administrative and instructional processes. The reason for this relationship could be that

in recent years, principals have participated in numerous training programs and workshops on the code of ethical conduct, which has provided principals with modern and diverse methods and strategies for dealing with teachers and stimulating their energies and abilities in a way that benefits the educational process. Perhaps this is due to the constant monitoring by those involved. Principals are legally accountable for the level of school performance, so they must pay attention to utilizing the code of ethical conduct to increase their level of performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Maintaining Arab school principals' strong commitment to the code of ethical conduct in the areas of (the profession, students, the local community, and coworkers) inside the Green Line.
- Green Line school principals maintain a high level of school performance in (administration performance, school environment, learning and teaching, and social connections).
- Inviting school principals to evaluate the findings of research and studies on the code of ethical behavior in order to improve school performance.
- Conducting additional research on the code of ethical conduct among school leaders and relating it to variables such as teacher job performance.

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